

Two main changes expected when we go from a simple (MX) to a ternary complex (MXY), are (i) structural changes (i.e. changes in geometry) and (ii) changes in bond energy and mutual interaction of ligands. The second effect may arise from the effects of solvent and ionic strength (as also from statistical effects), change in bond strength, and steric hindrance due to size of the ligand. In the present study the factors which might most probably affect the stability of these mixed complexes are statistical, electrostatic and steric. From a comparison of the dimensionless disproportionation constant K_s for the following equilibrium it is found that the mixed ligand complex is more stable than what might be expected from purely statistical considerations.

The enhanced stability might therefore be attributed to factors such as steric and electrostatic.

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Polarographic Study of Thorium(IV) and Uranyl(II) Complexes with DL-Ornithine Hydrochloride

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AMINO acids have a wide variety of biological, pharmaceutical and other chemical uses, and have been reported to form complexes with some metals. Hence their importance has grown. The polarographic behaviour of some amino acids and their metal complexes have already been studied by Saxena *et al*¹⁻³.

This communication reports the polarographic behaviour of uranyl(II) and Th(IV) complexes with DL-ornithine hydrochloride, for which no reference could be found in the literature.

Thorium(IV) reduces irreversibly at d.m.e. in presence of DL-ornithine hydrochloride and produces a diffusion controlled wave. The values of kinetic parameters - transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K'_{t,h}$) have been determined by Koutecky's method⁴ as extended by Meites and Israel⁵.

Uranyl(II) reduces reversibly at d.m.e. in presence of DL-ornithine hydrochloride and produces a diffusion controlled wave. The composition and stability constants of the metal complexes have been studied by Lingane method⁷.

Experimental

DL-Ornithine hydrochloride (DOH) was supplied by B. D. H. Chemicals Ltd., Poole, England and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Their solutions were prepared in double distilled conductivity water. Triton-X-100 (0.002 percent) was used as maxima suppressor. The ionic strength was maintained by NaClO_4 .

Polarographic measurements were made on a Toshniwal polarograph, equipped with thermostated H-cell and saturated calomel electrode. Capillary had the characteristics in 0.1 M NaClO_4 at -0.5 volts vs S. C. E. with h_{H_2} value of 40 cm, $m = 2.895$ mg/sec, $t = 2.40$ seconds.

The values of kinetic parameters were determined from the polarograms of the solutions containing 0.1 m M Th^{4+} , 0.1 M NaClO_4 , 0.002 percent Triton-X-100 and various concentrations of DOH.

Results and Discussion

Uranyl-DOH complex at d.m.e. gives a well defined wave in aqueous medium. Reduction is found to be diffusion controlled one electron

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reversible step as evident from the constant value of $i_d/\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ within experimental conditions, and from the values of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ which were 0.06 ± 0.001 V agreeing with the theoretical value for one electron transfer process.

The cathodic shift in $E_{1/2}$ coupled with decrease in diffusion current (i_d) on increasing ligand concentration from 0.0015 M to 0.012 M, shows the complex formation. The plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ results in a straight line. Hence the complex formed consists of only one species. The number of ligand/metal ion, J , has been determined from the slope of the plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ [Fig. 1(a)] at 25° and is $1.09 \approx 1.0$. The stability constant of the metal complex has been studied by Lingane method⁷. The intercept of the plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ [Fig. 1(a)] on the ordinate axis at $(-\log C_x = 0)$ gives $\left(\frac{0.0591}{n}\right) \log K_c$ from which $\log K_c$ is found to be 3.672.

Fig. 1(a). Plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ for UO_2^{2+} -DOH system.

Fig. 1(b). Plot of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$ at different concentrations of DOH.

The plots of $\log (i/i_d - i)$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$ [Fig. 1(b)] for Th^{4+} in DOH were linear but their slopes were not in agreement with the theoretical values for reversible wave, indicating the irreversible nature of the waves. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ are linear indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the waves. With increase in DOH concentration, the $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative potential showing the complex formation between the metal ion and the ligand, whereas i_d decreases indicating that the aquo-thorium ions differ in size from their complexes with DOH.

The values of kinetic parameters, transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^\circ$), for the electrode reaction have been determined by applying Koutecky's theoretical treatment as extended by Meites and Israel⁸. The kinetic parameters of Th-DOH system in aqueous solution were calculated by using equations (1) and (2)

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log i/(i_d - i) \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$E_{1/2} = 0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^\circ t^{1/2}}{D_o^{1/2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

($E_{d.e.}$ and $E_{1/2}$ are referred to S. C. E.)

The value of αn was obtained from slope

$-\frac{0.05412}{\alpha n}$ of the straight line of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log$

$(i/i_d - i)$ [Fig. 1(b)]. The intercept of the same plot gave the value of $E_{1/2}$, which was used to calculate $K_{f,h}^\circ$ at different concentrations of the ligand (Table 1). Since 't' does not vary appreciably over the range of potential covered by the rising part of the curve due to the complexed Th^{4+} ion, it was not considered necessary to apply the correction for t^6 .

TABLE 1—VALUES OF i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn AND $K_{f,h}^\circ$ FOR Th^{4+} -DOH SYSTEM AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF DOH AT 25° [Fig. 1(b)]

Concn. of ligand mM	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ (volts)	$D_o \times 10^6$	αn	$K_{f,h}^\circ \times 10^{10}$ cm/sec
2	1.3	-1.285	5.193	0.7528	0.648
4	1.2	-1.290	4.426	0.7288	1.800
6	1.2	-1.297	4.426	0.7047	2.844

Table 1 shows that the values of α and $K_{f,h}^\circ$ are affected by the concentration of the ligand because of the change in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d with increase in the concentration of complexing agent.

The half wave potential shifts towards more positive value with increase in temperature (Table 2) [Fig. 1(c)] showing the easier reduction of the complex at higher temperature which is in accordance with the irreversible nature of the electrode processes.

Fig 1(c). Plot of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $-E_d e.$ at different temperatures for Th_4^+ -DOH system.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn AND $K_{f,h}^0$ FOR Th_4^+ -DOH SYSTEM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES [Fig. 1(c)]

Temperature (°C)	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$	Temperature coefficient (percent per deg)	$D_0 \times 10^6$	αn	$K_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
25	1.3	1.285	—	5.193	0.7526	6.148×10^{-17}
30	1.5	1.280	2.865	6.915	0.8130	7.109×10^{-18}
35	1.7	1.270	2.683	8.880	0.9173	1.927×10^{-19}

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Substituted Benzaldehydes by KMnO_4 in Buffer Medium

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In our earlier paper¹ we reported on the kinetics of oxidation of *p*-nitro benzaldehydes by permanganate. We have extended the work on kinetics of

oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by permanganate in buffer medium to various substituted benzaldehydes namely *o*-Cl, *o*-CH₃, *o*-NO₂, *m*-CH₃, *m*-NO₂, 2,4-dichloro, 2,6-dichloro and 2,4-dinitro. An attempt has also been made to verify the general acid catalysis, relative rate of buffer activity with the same substrate, substituent effect, order of reactivity for isomeric benzaldehydes, evaluation of kinetic parameters, steric effects and quantitative calculation of steric interaction energies.

Results and Discussion

Wiberg^{2,3} studied oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by KMnO_4 in neutral medium and proposed a mechanism. In order to verify the general acid catalysis for the above aldehydes, experiments were carried out at constant pH, temperature and ionic strength but at different concentrations of buffer. The buffers selected were pyrophosphate, dihydrogen phosphate and acetate. Other buffers could not be used as they were oxidised by permanganate. The second order rate constants as a function of buffer concentrations are given in Table 1 for *ortho*-nitro compound in three buffers as an example. It was found that increase in buffer concentration increased the rate of reaction for all substrates in three buffers. This confirms that the title reaction undergoes general acid catalysis. To find out the relative rate of buffer activity experiments were done with the same substrate in different buffers under similar conditions. The results given in Table 1 show that the relative rate of buffer activity was found to be pyrophosphate > dihydrogen phosphate > acetate.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF BUFFER CONCENTRATION ON RATE CONSTANT IN PERMANGANATE-*o*-NO₂ BENZALDEHYDE REACTION

$[\text{RCHO}]_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; $[\text{MnO}_4^-]_0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; pH=6.5; $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M}$; Temp.=35°

$[\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-]$	k_2	$[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-]$	k_2	$[\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}]$	k_2
0.20	0.20	0.20	0.28	0.020	0.25
0.15	0.18	0.15	0.24	0.015	0.22
0.10	0.16	0.10	0.19	0.010	0.19
0.05	0.11	0.05	0.15	0.005	0.14
0.01	0.08	0.01	0.10	0.0025	0.12

Units of $k_2 = 1. \text{m}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$.

The substituent effect on the reaction was studied at constant pH, temperature, and buffer concentration for the above substituted benzaldehydes and the rate constants are given in Table 2. The following substituent effect was observed in dihydrogen phosphate buffer of 0.01 M at 25° when pH is 6.5.

$p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2 > \text{H} > p\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-CH}_3 > o\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-Cl} > o\text{-Cl} > o\text{-CH}_3$. It was found from the substituent effect that electron withdrawing substituents enhance the rate of reaction while electron donating substituents reduce it. The order of reactivity for a given isomeric benzaldehydes was *para* > *meta* > *ortho*. This shows that *ortho* compounds are slower